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Generating hydrographic products with GRASS GIS: A hands-on workshop on the Hydrography90m methodology

Giuseppe Amatulli^{1,2}

¹Yale University, School of the Environment, 195 Prospect Street, New Haven, CT, 06511, USA

²Spatial Ecology, 35A, Hazlemere Road, Penn, Buckinghamshire, HP10 8AD, UK.
e-mail giuseppe.amatulli@yale.edu;
g.amatulli@spatial-ecology.net

Abstract - In this workshop, we will demonstrate the methodology developed by Amatulli [1] for creating the Hydrography90m dataset, using GRASS GIS and its hydrological modules.

I. GRASS GIS FEATURES

GRASS GIS (Geographic Resources Analysis Support System) is a powerful, open-source geographic information system that functions both as a geoprocessing engine and a comprehensive platform for spatial data analysis. It offers an extensive library of over 800 modules designed for a broad array of applications, including terrain modeling, hydrological analysis, land cover classification, remote sensing, and time-series geospatial analytics.

In the context of hydrology, GRASS GIS provides robust algorithms for flow accumulation, stream network extraction, and basin delineation. Its watershed and stream analysis tools allow users to derive detailed physical characteristics of catchments and drainage networks, supporting advanced environmental modeling and water resource management.

One of the standout features of GRASS GIS is its flexible, modular architecture. It supports multiple user interfaces, including a desktop Graphical User Interface (GUI), a powerful command-line interface (CLI), a C-based programming API, and bindings for Python. Integration with the R ecosystem is possible via the rgrass package (available on CRAN), and GRASS can also be used as a processing engine within QGIS, enabling smooth interoperability across platforms.

II. WORKSHOP CONTENTS

The workshop material is available at: https://spatial-ecology.net/docs/build/html/GRASS/grass_hydro_colab.html and

will also be distributed as a Jupyter Notebook during the workshop. Participants will have the opportunity to follow the notebook either in the Google Colab environment or on their local Linux machines. A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from South America (1km resolution) will be provided and used throughout the workshop.

Figure 1. The irregular tiling system (ITS, in red) overlaid with the DEM

The main focus of the workshop will be on the use of an Irregular Tiling System (ITS) (Fig. 1) to derive seamless hydrography layers from large DEMs, following the methodology developed by Amatulli [1] for creating the Hydrography90m dataset. The use of the ITS helps to overcome the high RAM requirements of the *r.watershed* (and *r.stream.**) GRASS command when generating seamless hydrographies layers.

A. Flow routing algorithms

As first part of the workshop I will introduce the flow routing algorithms available in GRASS GIS. The flow accumulation operation performs a cumulative count of the number of grid cells (or other surface area units) that drain into outlets, given the terrain surface. Calculating flow accumulation involves three sequential algorithms: determining flow direction, addressing depressions and flat areas, and finally, calculating flow accumulation. In GRASS GIS the flow routing algorithms are implemented in the *r.watershed* command. The most widely used algorithm is the single-flow (D8) [2] algorithm that assigns flow from a focal grid cell to only one of the eight neighbouring grid cells with the steepest slope. This algorithm accumulates, or pools, the entire flow from one cell to another, producing artifacts and unrealistic stream channels. An alternative to the D8 is the multi-flow direction algorithm (MD8). The MD8 splits the flow into multiple directions as a function of the slope in each of the neighbouring grid cells [3, 4] and produces stream channel patterns closer to reality than D8 does. The MD8 is implemented in GRASS GIS with a variation of the so called nal Holmgren [5] method. Such method has been named “FD8” in the *r.watershed* manual, and we are going to implement in the following methodology.

B. Workshops computational steps.

The overall geo-data flow of the proposed workshop can be summarised in the following phases:

- splitting the South America DEM into smaller irregular tiles to achieve computational scalability;
- computing flow accumulation and direction, and the subsequent extraction of stream channels and basins;
- computing geophysical, morphological, and topological properties of the stream channels and basins.

1) First step: compute FD8 flow accumulation

The first step involves computing flow accumulation for each tile using *r.watershed* with the FD8 algorithm. This is followed by *r.stream.extract* to derive the stream network, and then *r.stream.basins* to delineate drainage basins.

This process results in two types of basins:

- Complete drainage basins that fall entirely within a tile, and
- Truncated drainage basins that extend beyond tile boundaries and are only partially included.

These partially included or truncated basins will be identified (and removed) by querying for those that intersected a tile border. This left only entire drainage basins and the associated flow accumulation. Finally, by merging the flow accumulation outputs from all tiles that contain only complete basins, we will produce a seamless flow accumulation map for the entire South American region (Fig. 2).

2) Second step: compute stream and basin using the seamless South America flow accumulation.

We will use the seamless South America flow accumulation map to recompute, for each tile, the drainage basins, flow direction, and stream network. This involves re-running *r.stream.extract*, followed by *r.stream.basins*, as described in the first step. This step resolves any inconsistencies or errors that may have occurred at tile borders, particularly those related to truncated drainage basins.

Figure 2. Seamless South America flow accumulation.

3) *Third step: mosaic drainage basins, streams segments, and flow direction.*

The final step of the computation consists of mosaicking the tiled drainage basins (Fig. 4), stream segments (Fig. 3), and flow direction layers to produce seamless continental datasets. These layers will be consistent with the previously generated seamless flow accumulation map for South America.

III. V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Figure 3. Seamless South America stream network.

Figure 4. Seamless South America drainage basins.